

PREVALENCE AND RISK FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH GESTATIONAL DIABETES MELLITUS AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN IN EMOHUA LOCAL GOVERNMENT OF RIVERS STATE.

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Abstract: *This study aimed to assess the prevalence and risk factors associated with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) among pregnant women in the Emohua local government of Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional design. The study population comprised of pregnant women attending an antenatal clinic in the Emohua local government area. The sample size for this study was 400, and data were obtained using a simple random sampling method by balloting without replacement. The instrument for data collection was a proforma data collection form titled “Prevalence and Risk Factors associated with Gestational Diabetes among Pregnant women in Emohua Local Government, Rivers State”. The data collected from this study was collated and analyzed using the Statistical Products for Service Solution (SPSS), the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the demographic data, age-adjusted incidence of GDM was calculated using logistic regression, and multivariate logistic regression analysis was used to identify risk factors associated with GDM. The results showed that the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State was low (16.6%), but there was high relationship between age, obesity, family history of diabetes, polycystic ovarian syndrome, history of GDM, prior large-for-gestation age birth and gestational diabetes mellitus. The results also showed a significant relationship between age and GDM [$f(1,289) = 289.57, p < 0.05$], obesity and GDM [$f(1,289) = 194.66, p < 0.05$], family history of diabetes and GDM [$f(1,289) = 201.92, p < 0.05$], polycystic ovarian syndrome and GDM [$f(1,289) = 198.34, p < 0.05$], history of GDM and GDM [$f(1,289) = 198.25, p < 0.05$] and between prior large-for-gestation age and GDM [$f(1,289) = 247.94, p < 0.05$]. The government should support ongoing research to better understand the risk factors and prevalence of GDM, establish robust surveillance systems to monitor trends, and evaluate the impact of prevention strategies.*

Introduction

The term gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) refers to varying degrees of glucose intolerance that are initially noticed during pregnancy. GDM is typically, but not always, mild and asymptomatic and is identified by screening pregnant women for clinical risk factors and testing for impaired glucose tolerance. The wide range of physiological and genetic abnormalities that characterize diabetes outside pregnancy may be the cause of GDM. In fact, women with GDM are more susceptible to acquiring or having diabetes even when they are not pregnant, (Buchanan & Xiang, 2015).

Historically, O'Sullivan discovered in the 1960s that the likelihood of developing diabetes following pregnancy was correlated with the degree of glucose intolerance during pregnancy. He established cut-off values (roughly 2 standard deviations) for diagnosing glucose intolerance during pregnancy using fundamentally statistical criteria for the interpretation of oral glucose tolerance tests (OGTTs) and this is the criteria recommended by the American Diabetes Association (American Diabetes Association, 2014). GDM is diagnosed at 24-28 wk of gestation using a "one-step strategy" (75-grams 2-hr oral glucose tolerance test). The test should be done within 8-14 hr of overnight fasting. A diagnosis of GDM can be made when one of the following values is met or exceeded in the one-step strategy: 0-h (fasting) ≥ 92 mg/dL; 1-hr ≥ 180 mg/dL; or 2-hr ≥ 153 mg/dL (American Diabetes Association, 2015). Some researchers have argued that all pregnant women should be

screened for gestational diabetes mellitus because 40%–60% of affected women have no symptoms (Ewenighi et al., 2013). The Canadian Diabetes Association and the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists recommend universal screening. The U.S. However, the Preventive Services Task Force and the Cochrane Collaboration concluded that there was inadequate evidence to recommend for or against screening for gestational diabetes (David & Robert, 2019). The National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) guideline recommends using risk factors to screen for gestational diabetes mellitus in a healthy population. The prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus is low in the absence of related risk factors, indicating that targeted screening would be cost-effective (Ugege et al., 2013). The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends a two-stage screening process for diabetes mellitus during pregnancy. All pregnant women should be tested for glucosuria during their first antenatal visit, and a positive result indicates that they should be evaluated further with 75 grams OGTT.

Given the serious risk and damaging health impacts of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM), maternal health is receiving several research attentions. GDM is a leading health disease in pregnant women. According to Kim et al. (2021), it is the most prevalent metabolic disorder and can affect up to 25% of pregnant women. Pregnancy is a sensitive time that can affect the long-term health of both pregnant women and their unborn children. Cancer and diabetes

mellitus are the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide and women with diabetes mellitus are more likely to develop breast cancer (Choudhury & Rajeswari, 2021).

Diabetes has become the third "silent killer" in the globe after cancer and cardiovascular disease due to its rising morbidity and mortality rates among the human race, (Madhuri & Ramachandra, 2017). Diabetes was always thought to be a single disease; however, today's medical specialists have discovered that diabetes contains many heterogeneous diseases and can cause a wide range of illnesses. Diabetes increases a woman's vulnerability to reproductive illnesses; the main causes of reproductive issues in patients with diabetes include obesity, polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), and hyperinsulinemia (Anand et al., 2017).

Diabetes is of three types: Type 1 diabetes, Type 2 diabetes (T2DM), and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM). T2DM was seen in 90–95% of cases of adult diabetes (Sole, 2021). Pregnancy-related diabetes mellitus (PRDM) frequently interferes with fetal growth and maternal health. Abortions and miscarriages are more common in diabetic women. It is a major cause of infant mortality or premature births (Bequer et al., 2017). The most common maternal complication of GDM is Cesarean section. The main complication for newborns is macrosomia and its traumatic consequences. In the long run, mother and baby remain at increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) in approximately 50% of cases (Zhu & Zhang, 2016). Numerous medications were used to treat

most complications. However, a developing fetus is known to be directly or indirectly impacted by some medications. Therefore, phytochemical-based medicines with no adverse effects are being developed to improve the treatment of GDM (Shen et al., 2020). Despite tremendous progress in therapeutic research, diabetes continues to be a major global health issue .

According to predictions from the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), 629 million people would have diabetes by the year 2045, up from an estimated 425 million in 2017. By 2025, it is anticipated that 1 in 3 adults in the United States (USA) would develop diabetes. Type 2 diabetes is becoming more common in adults, particularly among young women diagnosed during their reproductive years (Knox et al., 2014). The prevalence of GDM varies by race, ethnicity, age, body composition, and screening and diagnostic criteria globally (Kim et al., 2021). In the United States, approximately 1 in every 10 pregnant women is affected, and nearly 90% of diabetes occurrences during pregnancy are GDM. The prevalence is even higher among Asian women (Li et al., 2017). In sub-Saharan Africa, the prevalence of GDM varies between 1% and 13.9% (Macauley et al., 2014). A more recent meta-analysis using data from 33 studies estimated a gestational diabetes prevalence of 9% in sub-Saharan Africa (95% CI, 7-12%) (Natamba et al., 2020). The prevalence of GDM in Nigeria was 0.5 – 38% and the pooled prevalence was 11.0% (95% CI 8-13) which is higher than that in Africa. The most frequently reported determinants of GDM were previous macrosomic babies, maternal obesity, family history of diabetes,

previous miscarriage, and advanced maternal age (Azeez et al., 2021).

Although normal glucose regulation often returns promptly after birth in most women, those with GDM have a sevenfold increased chance of later developing Type 2 diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). T2DM is a rising public health concern associated with a number of serious health issues that reduce patients' life expectancy and quality of life (Eades et al., 2015). This study explored the following risk factors for GDM; advanced age, obesity, ethnicity, family history of diabetes, history of GDM, polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), and prior large-for-gestation (LGA) births. Failure to assess the prevalence and the associated risk factors, both modifiable and non-modifiable, of gestational diabetes mellitus will lead to grave negative outcomes. The adverse effect of gestational diabetes mellitus affects both mother and child, and the country's health system is not equipped to deal with such public health issue.

The residents of Emohua are predisposed to gestational diabetes mellitus first by virtue of belonging to the black race. More importantly, the rising incidence of obesity and diabetes mellitus due to lifestyle changes predisposes most women in the local government to gestational diabetes mellitus. A high prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus will negatively impact the life of the women and children of Emohua. Despite these severe consequences, insufficient research work has been done to determine the prevalence and identify the risk factors associated with gestational diabetes

mellitus in Rivers State, specifically in the Emohua local government.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence and identify the risk factors associated with gestational diabetes mellitus in Rivers State, specifically in the Emohua local government. In specific terms, this study sought to

1. Determine the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area.
2. to ascertain the relationship between age and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State.
3. Examine relationship between obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in Emohua local government area of Rivers State.
4. Determine the relationship between family history of diabetes mellitus and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area.
5. Identify the relationship between polycystic ovarian syndrome and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State.
6. Determine the relationship between history of GDM and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State.
7. Examine the relationship between prior large-for-gestation age and gestational diabetes

mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed to guide the study.

8. What is the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area?

9. What is the relationship between age and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area?

10. What is the relationship between obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in Rivers State's Emohua local government area?

11. What is the relationship between family history of diabetes and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area?

12. What is the relationship between polycystic ovarian syndrome and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in Rivers State's Emohua local government area?

13. What is the relationship between history of GDM and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State?

14. What is the relationship between prior large-for-gestation age and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in Rivers State's Emohua local government area?

Methodology

The study was conducted in Emohua Local government Area (LGA) of Rivers State. The study adopted an institutional-based cross-sectional research design and a proforma data collection form titled "Prevalence and Risk Factors associated with Gestational Diabetes among Pregnant women in Emohua Local Government, Rivers State (PRFAGDPW)" was used to obtain data from the medical records of pregnant women with GDM. Ethical guidelines were followed in the use of patient records as anonymisation of cases were anonymised to protect the identity of each patient. The study population consisted of pregnant women residing in Emohua and visiting one of the health facilities for antenatal care in the Emohua local government area. Data were collected from 400 women using a simple random sampling method by balloting without replacement. The researcher used a validated questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.76. The data generated in this study through questionnaire were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to analyze the demographic data, age-adjusted incidence of GDM was calculated using logistic regression. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was used to identify the risk factors associated with GDM.

Result

Research Question 1: What is the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State?

Fig 1: Percentage distribution showing the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM)

Fig. 1 presents the percentage distribution showing prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus. The results showed that less than half (16.6%) of the patients had gestational diabetes, while the majority (83.4%) did not have gestational diabetes. Thus, the prevalence of

gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State was low (16.6%).

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between age and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 1: Regression analysis on the relationship between age and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government Area.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error in the Estimate	Decision
1	.71	.50	.49	130.34	High relationship

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high, and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in Rivers State’s Emohua Local Government Area?

Table 2: Regression analysis on the relationship between obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error in the Estimate	Decision
1	.63	.40	.40	142.56	High relationship

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high, and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 2 illustrates the relationship between obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area. The results indicated a high positive relationship between obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.63$). The result further showed that obesity contributed

40.2% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.402$). Thus, the relationship between obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high.

Research Question 4: What is the relationship between family history of diabetes and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua Local Government Area?

Table 3: Regression analysis on the relationship between family history of diabetes and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error in the Estimate	Decision
1	.64	.411	.40	141.51	High relationship

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high, and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 3 illustrates the relationship between family history of diabetes and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area. The results indicated a high positive relationship between family history of diabetes and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.64$). The results further

showed that a family history of diabetes contributed 41.1% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.411$). Thus, the relationship between family history of diabetes and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high.

Research Question 5: What is the relationship between polycystic ovarian syndrome and gestational diabetes mellitus

among pregnant women in Rivers State's Emohua Local Government Area?

Table 4: Regression analysis on the relationship between polycystic ovarian syndrome and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error in the Estimate	Decision
1	.64	.405	.40	141.51	High relationship

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high, and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 4 illustrates the relationship between polycystic ovarian syndrome and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area. The results indicated a high positive relationship between polycystic ovarian syndrome and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.64$). The result further showed that polycystic ovarian syndrome

contributed 40.5% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.405$). Thus, the relationship between polycystic ovarian syndrome and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high.

Research Question 6: What is the relationship between a history of GDM and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 4.5: Regression analysis on relationship between history of GDM and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error in the Estimate	Decision
1	.63	.40	.40	142.03	High relationship

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high, and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 5 illustrates the relationship between GDM history and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area. The results indicated a high

positive relationship between history of GDM and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.63$). The results further showed that a history of GDM contributed 40.7% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.407$). Thus, the relationship between history of GDM and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant

women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high.

Research Question 7: What is the relationship between prior large-for-gestation age and

Table 6: Regression analysis on the relationship between prior large-for-gestation age and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua local government area.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error in the Estimate	Decision
1	.68	.46	.46	135.30	High relationship

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high, and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 6 illustrates the relationship between prior large-for-gestation age and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area. The results indicated a high positive relationship between prior large-for-gestation age and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.68$). The results further showed that prior large-for-gestation age contributed 46.2% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.462$). Thus, the relationship between prior large-for-gestation age and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high.

Discussion of the Findings

The results showed that less than half (16.6%) of the patients had gestational diabetes, while the majority (83.4%) did not. Thus, the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State was low (16.6%). The findings of this

gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Rivers State Emohua Local Government Area?

study are in line with those of Nigatu et al. (2022), who showed that the prevalence of GDM among pregnant women attending the antenatal care clinic of St. Paul's Hospital Millennium Medical College, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, was 16.9%. This was also supported by the findings of Azeez et al. (2021), who showed that GDM prevalence ranged from 0.5% to 38% in Nigeria, and the combined prevalence was 11.0% (95% CI 8-13). To support this finding, Ogu et al. (2022) showed that the prevalence of GDM in a major City in Nigeria was 5.2%. The prevalence rates of GDM in the first, second and third trimesters were 4.9%, 4.2%, and 6.7%, respectively. In addition, John et al. (2020) revealed that the prevalence of GDM at the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital (RSUTH), Port Harcourt, Nigeria, was 10.5%. However, Mazumder et al. (2022) revealed a much higher prevalence of GDM of 35% in Bangladesh in the early weeks of pregnancy, but the rates were less prevalent in the later weeks of pregnancy than in the early weeks.

The results indicated a high positive relationship between age and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.71$). The results further showed that age contributed 50.0% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.500$). Thus, the relationship between age and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high. The findings of this study are in line with those of Nigatu et al. (2022), who found that age affected the prevalence of GDM and that GDM was more prevalent in older age groups (AOR = 2.75, 95% CI: 1.03, 7.35 for 30–34 years old and AOR = 4.98, 95% CI: 1.703, 14.578 for ≥ 35 years old). Li et al. (2020) showed that the incidence and age-adjusted incidence of GDM in Qingdao were 17.42% and 17.45%, respectively. The incidence of GDM appeared to increase steadily with age in all pre-pregnancy BMI groups (all $P < 0.05$). The odds ratio (OR) of pre-pregnancy BMI ≥ 30 kg/m² at the age of <30 years and 30–34 years was 1.30 (95% CI: 0.74–2.28, $P = 0.36$) and 3.21 (95% CI: 2.28–4.52, $P < 0.0001$), respectively. This indicated that a pre-pregnancy BMI ≥ 30 kg/m² had a stronger effect on GDM in the group aged 30–34 years than in those aged 30 years old. Also in support of this finding is the work of Amiri et al. (2018) which identified advanced maternal age as one of 4 significant risk factors of GDM (OR = 1.24, 95% CI = 1.13–1.35).

The results indicated high positive relationship between obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.63$). The result further showed that obesity contributed 40.2% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.402$). Thus,

the relationship between obesity and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high. The results of this study are in line with the findings of Yen et al. (2019), who showed that overweight/obesity was associated with clustering of metabolic risk factors of GDM, including high fasting plasma glucose, high HbA1c, insulin resistance, high plasma triglyceride, and elevated blood pressure in FPV ($p < 0.05$). The odds ratios of HbA1c and diastolic blood pressure were higher in overweight/obese women than in normal-weight women. Additionally, Larrabure-Torrealva et al. (2018) showed that the prevalence of obesity was 24.4%, and after adjusting for confounders, mid-pregnancy obesity was associated with a 1.64-fold increased odds of GDM (OR: 1.64; 95% CI: 1.03–2.61).

The results indicated a high positive relationship between family history of diabetes and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.64$). The results further showed that a family history of diabetes contributed 41.1% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.411$). Thus, the relationship between family history of diabetes and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high. In support of this finding, Ogu et al. (2022) stated that adjusting for confounding variables, family history of diabetes was found to be a significant predictor of GDM among the study participants. To buttress these findings, Lewandowska (2021) provided a detailed analysis of the influence of family history of diabetes on GDM; women with

diabetes in the father had a 3.68-fold increase in GDM-1 risk (AOR-b = 3.68 (2.23–6.07)), and women with diabetes in the mother had a 2.13-fold increase in GDM-1 risk (AOR-b = 2.13 (1.1–4.14)) and a 4.73-fold increase in GDM-2 risk (AOR-b = 4.73 (1.26–17.77)). Women with diabetes in the grandmother had a 2.34-fold increase in GDM-1 risk (AOR-b = 2.34 (1.29–4.24)). The analyses in the subgroups of BMI categories showed that diabetes in the father was also an independent risk factor of GDM in the subgroup of pregnant women with normal BMI. The results indicated a high positive relationship between polycystic ovarian syndrome and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.64$). The result further showed that polycystic ovarian syndrome contributed 40.5% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.405$). Thus, the relationship between polycystic ovarian syndrome and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high. The findings of this study are agreement with those of Li et al. (2021), who showed that incidence of GDM in patients with PCOS was 23.98%. Age ≥ 30 years (odds ratio (OR) 2.418, 95% CI 1.181–3.784), body mass index ≥ 24 kg/m² (OR 1.973, 95% CI 1.266–3.121), insulin resistance index ≥ 22.69 (OR 2.491, 95% CI 1.193–4.043), fasting insulin ≥ 22.71 mIU/L (OR 2.508, 95% CI 1.166–5.057), testosterone ≥ 2.85 nmol/L (OR 1.821, 95% CI 1.104–2.762), androstenedione ≥ 6.63 nmol/L (OR 1.954, 95% CI 1.262–2.844), sex hormone-binding protein < 64.22 nmol/L (OR 1.497, 95% CI 1.028–2.016) were the independent risk factors of GDM in patients with PCOS (all

$P < .05$). Additionally, Mustaniemi et al. (2018) showed that the prevalence of PCOS was 10.4% among women with GDM and 7.4% among non-diabetics (OR 1.44, 95% CI: 1.05–1.97), but PCOS was not found to be an independent risk factor for GDM after adjustments for participants' age and pre-pregnancy BMI (OR 1.07, 95% CI: 0.74–1.54).

The results indicated a high positive relationship between history of GDM and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.63$). The results further showed that a history of GDM contributed 40.7% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.407$). Thus, the relationship between history of GDM and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high. This is in agreement with the result of Preda et al. (2022), who showed statistically significant differences between the GDM and non-GDM groups in terms of the presence of GDM during previous pregnancies (7.8% vs. 0%), history of fetal macrosomia (13.7% vs. 0%), HBP before pregnancy (9.8% vs. 0%), gestational HBP (17.6% vs. 0%), and glycemia value at first medical visit (79.37 ± 9.34 mg/dl vs. 71.39 ± 9.16 mg/dl). Also in support of the finding is the work of Song et al. (2023) which showed the incidence of GDM in subsequent pregnancy was 48.9% (490/1002) in women with GDM history and 16.1% (835/5202) in women without GDM history. John et al. (2020) also revealed that a positive history of GDM in previous pregnancy was the only independent risk factor for GDM among pregnant women attending the antenatal

clinic at RSUTH ($p=0.04$, Adjusted OR: 26.89, 95% CI 2.86 to 252.61).

The results indicated a high positive relationship between prior large-for-gestation age and gestational diabetes mellitus ($r = 0.68$). The results further showed that prior large-for-gestation age contributed 46.2% of the variance in gestational diabetes mellitus ($R^2 = 0.462$). Thus, the relationship between prior large-for-gestation age and gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua Local Government Area was high. The results of this study support the findings of Azeez et al. (2021) in a systematic review that showed that the most frequently reported determinants of GDM were previous macrosomic (LGA) babies and previous miscarriage. In support of this study, Miller and Lim (2021) showed that macrosomia significantly increased the risk of GDM later in life in the chi-square test and logistic regression. Independent of GDM, women who deliver a macrosomic infant have a 20% higher chance of developing diabetes than women who do not.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus among pregnant women in the Emohua local government area of Rivers State was low, but there was a high relationship between age, obesity, family history of diabetes, polycystic ovarian syndrome, history of GDM, prior large-for-gestation age and gestational diabetes mellitus. The relationship between the variables and GDM was also statistically significant.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Ministry of Health should develop and implement a comprehensive risk assessment tool that considers factors such as maternal age, obesity, family history of diabetes, and prior GDM to identify high-risk women who may benefit from intensified monitoring and interventions.
2. The primary health care development agency should help reduce the prevalence of GDM by offering educational programs and counseling to pregnant women regarding the risks of GDM, its potential consequences, and prevention and management strategies, including glucose monitoring information and treatment benefits if diagnosed.
3. The state ministry of health should provide a holistic approach to treatment and support by establishing multidisciplinary care teams that include obstetricians, endocrinologists, dietitians, and nurses to manage pregnant women with GDM at special health centers.
4. The ministry of health should establish a structured postpartum follow-up program for women with GDM, with regular glucose tolerance assessments, and provide education on the increased risk of type 2 diabetes and the importance of postpartum health.
5. Health-related agencies should increase awareness of GDM and its risk factors by engaging communities and health care providers and developing partnerships with community

organizations to promote education and prevention efforts.

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Ethical consideration: No ethical consideration was required for this study.

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